

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

D4.5 FINAL SHERPA ONLINE REPOSITORY UPDATE

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D4.5 FINAL SHERPA ONLINE REPOSITORY UPDATE

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Authors	Penny Zafiraki, Hercules Panoutsopoulos, Borja Espejo Garcia, Anna Selini Petropoulou (AUA)
Work Package Leader	AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (AUA)
Project Coordinator	ECORYS

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Executive Summary

This document is the report for the [Sherpa Online Repository Updates](#). It has been created to fulfil the needs of the project's Deliverable 4.5 and it summarises the updates carried out on the SHERPA repository and web crawler as well.

This document details the interactions of the tasks in Work Package 4 in relation to the work completed in the repository. The repository's data and information availability are presented, and longevity considerations are made. Furthermore, this report provides an overview of the topics that are added on an annual basis as well as a more detailed navigation to the information on the ongoing and past research projects presented through the repository.

The online repository has been developed and managed by the Agricultural University of Athens.

1. Introduction

This report presents the results of the work done on updating and upgrading the [SHERPA online repository](#) for the storage and retrieval of information and ready-to-be-used knowledge about rural-related research projects. The SHERPA online repository has been continuously updated in terms of the content provided and improvements in its operation and functionality since its initial release at the end of the first year of the project. This report presents and explains that development work.

The work carried out was under Work Package 4 ('Stocktaking of relevant past and on-going project results'), and more specifically Task 4.3 ('Design, development, update and maintenance of SHERPA online repository') and Task 4.4 ('Stocktake of findings of relevant projects').

Task 4.3 is responsible for the design, development and operation of the repository that contributes to the MAP Discussion Papers and is linked to Task 4.4, the web crawler that provides information on new projects and project outputs by topic. Figure 1 illustrates the interaction between the two tasks.

Figure 1: Interactions between Tasks 4.3 & 4.4

Following the work already described in previous deliverable (D4.3), the final update of the SHERPA online repository is presented in the following sections of this report. Section 2 presents the objectives to be achieved, the benefits to users of accessing the repository and the data provided by the repository. Section 3 provides an overview of the information (projects, topics) available, and the updates made. In Section 4, updates and upgrades of the repository are presented and explained in terms of the technical work undertaken. These first upgrades follow on from a survey conducted in the first year of the project to obtain feedback on the web application for accessing the SHERPA data repository. Details of the maintenance and upgrade-related work for the SHERPA web crawler (i.e, the tool used to identify and retrieve project information and results) are also presented. A sustainability plan is presented in the last section (section 5) of the document.

2. Scope of the SHERPA online repository

The European Commission has set out a EU's Long-Term Vision for rural areas with the aim of developing a common European vision for 2040. This vision identifies challenges, opportunities, and areas for action towards stronger, more connected, resilient, and prosperous communities. In terms of strengthening rural areas across Europe, the SHERPA project contributed by collecting research-based knowledge and evidence and provided support for the formulation of recommendations for future policies and research relevant to EU rural areas. Such evidence relates to information and results available from more than 800 EU-funded, Research and Innovation projects associated with the SHERPA project's rural topics of focus. Section 3 of the report presents the data and findings.

The SHERPA online repository is a one-stop shop for data and information related to topics of interest and relevance to rural areas based on the findings and research outputs of projects funded by the European Union. It provides a unique collection of rural-related information and evidence for researchers, policymakers, representatives of public authorities/administrations, and rural citizens, enabling informed insights into the present and future of rural areas of Europe. The repository provides access to information and details of research projects extracted from the [CORDIS](#), [LIFE](#) and [EIP-AGRI](#) databases.

The SHERPA online repository system plays a key role in the SHERPA project, providing storage capacity for data produced and made available to research projects. The system facilitates stakeholder access and has a system designed to efficiently meet end-user needs. The objective is to identify, select and evaluate past and ongoing research projects and to ensure efficient and reliable access for stakeholders.

The SHERPA online repository is designed to target different types of end-users. These include members of the SHERPA consortium on their roles as scientific editors, review editors, and authors of the Discussion and Position papers, coordinators or members of research projects that are of interest to SHERPA and currently active, scientists and researchers, policy-makers, representatives of civil society, organisations, and citizens.

As shown in Figure 2, the repository can provide end-users with data displayed on a cartographic map showing the geographical distribution of SHERPA MAPs and their equivalents (such as Living Labs) for other projects in the Rural Cluster (e.g., Polirural, Desira,..). The map is implemented in ArcGIS Online¹, taking advantage of its features that allow users to zoom in on specific areas of interest, change the background and print outputs for use in other settings.

¹ ArcGIS Online is a secured, reliable geographic information system (GIS) delivered using the software-as-a-service (SaaS) model.

Figure 2: Cartographic map of multi-actor groups

3. Data and information available

This section provides an overview of the information available in the SHERPA online repository and the updates made to its content such as: information on the topics covered by the project each year, the projects available for each topic, and the projects available in the SHERPA online repository. The following subsections provide a detailed explanation of the information available under each of the above points, as well as the annual updates to this information.

3.1. SHERPA topics

During the lifetime of the project, nine topics were reviewed and debated by the MAPs. Figure 3 shows how a topic and information about the topic (topic description) was delivered from the SHERPA online repository.

Figure 3: Presentation of a topic in the SHERPA online repository.

One or more topics were tackled by the MAPs each year. The SHERPA online repository was updated to provide information on the selected topic(s) for that year. Table 1 presents the topic(s) and a brief description of each one added annually.

Table 1: Topics and descriptions

Project Year	Topic(s)	Description
Year 1 (2020)	Long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	The topic covers a wide range of factors identified by the MAPs such as demographic change, connectivity, poverty risk and limited access to services.
	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features	This topic deals with the diversity of life on Earth as it is essential for human survival and well-being. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the link between human health and ecosystem health, emphasising the need for sustainable supply chains and consumption patterns. Protecting and restoring biodiversity was identified as critical to building resilience and preventing future diseases.
Year 2 (2021)	Climate Change And Environmental Sustainability	The topic points out that climate change affects rural areas differently from urban areas due to land resources and agriculture, with implications for sectors such as forestry, fisheries and mining.
	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy	The topic covers labour markets, trends and employment potential in rural areas and their influence by factors such as global value chains that affect rural areas, but that diversified rural economies offer potential.
Year 3 (2022)	Social dimension of rural areas	The topic the social relationships between people that affect their lives and adaptation to challenges such as demographic change, poverty and limited access to basic amenities.
	Digitalisation in rural areas	The topic describes that rural areas face limited access to services, infrastructure and fast broadband, leading to social exclusion and poverty.
	Climate change and land use	The topic discusses the threats from climate change, and approaches climate-neutral, green and equitable continent, focusing on renewable energy, sustainable agriculture and biodiversity conservation.
	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains	The topic discusses issues of mistrust and a lack of solidarity in supply chain relationships hinder farmers' perceptions of asymmetric distribution. Interventions facilitate improved farm management, environmental sustainability and adaptation to climate change.
Year 4 (2023)	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes	The topic covers issues of empowerment of citizens, and regional and local institutions and decision-makers and its importance for cohesive EU, national, regional and local policies to address rural challenges and meet residents' needs.

Users of the repository could suggest new topics by clicking on the button on the repository home page. This triggers the display of a form (see Figure 3) asking for some information about the user (i.e. name,

email address, expertise), about the suggested topic (i.e. reason for the suggestion, keywords, etc.), and details of the MAP represented (if any). The user would then be asked to submit the form.

New MAP topic form

You may use this online form to suggest new topics for investigation and discussion within the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP) you represent. To do so, you need to provide a short rationale for your suggestion together with a list of keywords to be used for the search of Eu-funded R&I projects and project results of relevance to the topic.

Any **personal information** to be collected through this survey will be **kept confidential** and will be used **only for communication purposes** (for instance, getting into contact with the MAP member submitting a new topic request with the aim to share information or request any additional input for the better delivery of results). For any problems, concerns, or issues that may arise, you may **get in contact with us** by emailing us at sherparepository@gmail.com.

Name *

Type in your name following the pattern: First name, middle name (if any), last name (e.g., Mary Jane Johansson).

Κείμενο σύντομης απάντησης

Email address *

Type in a valid email address in order to be able to get in contact with you, if needed.

Κείμενο σύντομης απάντησης

Background/expertise

From the list available below, select the option that best describes your background/expertise.

- Educator/trainer
- Entrepreneur/SME representative
- Farmer
- Farmer advisor
- Forester
- NGO representative
- Policy maker

Figure 4: Topic Suggestion Form

3.2 Information about EU-funded Research and Innovation projects

When navigating the online repository, users can choose a specific topic. By clicking on that topic, users can access a list of EU-funded research and innovation projects of relevance. The information available for each project is the project logo, the project acronym, the start and end date of the project, a short summary, keywords, subtopics to which this project belongs, the project budget, and its website if available. An indicative example is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 5: Information available for the EU-funded Research and Innovation projects available from the SHERPA online repository.

The objective of the project is displayed as a short text. Links to the official project website and the project page in CORDIS are made available, as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 6: Available Information per Project

On the same page of the repository, additional information about the project is shown in Figure 6. The user can access the publicly available project outputs, categorised by type (e.g. scientific paper, presentation, briefing note).

Figure 7: Outputs Available per Project

As stated previously, the repository is updated on a yearly basis with the inclusion of new projects. Table 2 provides an overview of the number of projects added annually per topic tackled by the SHERPA MAPs, which are listed in Annex 1. Some of the projects may fit into more than one topic. The repository remains active with ongoing updates and maintenance until the project's completion.

Table 2: Annual project additions per year

Project Year	Topic(s)	Number of Added Projects
Year 1 (2020)	Long-term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	226
	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features	98
Year 2 (2021)	Climate Change And Environmental Sustainability	48
	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy	78
Year 3 (2022)	Digitalisation in rural areas	57
	Climate change and land use	79
	Social dimension of rural areas	56

	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains	105
Year 4 (2023)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes 	29

An important aspect of the SHERPA repository's information is the inclusion of four other rural-related projects: DESIRA, MOVING, POLIRURAL, and RURALIZATION. This information was provided as part of a rural project cluster to enhance collaboration, knowledge exchange, and communication within the Rural Cluster of Horizon 2020. Additionally, it aims to contribute to future rural policy recommendations. As some of these projects were completed before the end of the SHERPA project, it was decided to adopt a broader approach and extend the information provided to include more recent projects. So, two new projects have been added to the section, starting in September 2023. These are FUTURAL, which aims to develop and showcase community-led, socially responsible innovations in various rural areas by implementing technological and business methods, and RURACTIVE, which will create smart, community-driven, tailor-made, place-based and inclusive solutions across 12 pilot cases throughout Europe to promote a fair and sustainable transition of rural regions. It is worth noting that these projects are oriented towards enhancing rural development.

The information available about these projects is: the acronym, context, information about the project, duration, website and social media channels (for example, see Figure 8).

MOVING - Mountain Valorisation through Interconnectedness and Green Growth

Context

Mountains cover 36% of the European area and have an important role in the provision of public and private goods. Despite their relevance in both ecological and socioeconomic terms, there is a lack of updated and comparable knowledge about many aspects of these regions affecting their management and sustainability.

A deeper understanding of how the context, trends and potential evolution of mountain communities, territories and businesses, is needed to design new policies that protect mountain areas from the existing threats of climate change, helping them to seize emerging opportunities.

About the project

MOVING (Mountain Valorisation through Interconnectedness and Green growth) aims to build capacities and co-develop – through a bottom-up participatory process that involves value chain actors, stakeholders and policy-makers – relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or upgraded/upscaled value chains that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas to climate change.

MOVING will carry out an in-depth assessment of vulnerability and resilience of land use, production systems and value chains in 23 mountain regions.

The project strongly relies on a citizen-science-policy interface organised around a multi-actor approach: a Community of Practice formed by 23 multi-actor platforms and an EU platform; a Virtual Research Environment to foster online interactions among actors; and new visual tools to make the information accessible to different audiences.

Duration: 1 September 2020 – 31 August 2024

Find out more about MOVING on the project's website: moving-h2020.eu

Social media channels

Figure 8: Information provided per project in RUR 1-2 Cluster

4. Update and upgrade of the SHERPA online repository and web crawler

4.1. Internal evaluation of the SHERPA online repository

In Year 1 of the project, after the first release of the repository, a survey was launched to collect feedback about the web application that had been developed to provide access to the SHERPA data repository. The web crawler tool devised for the SHERPA project proved to be an effective method for this task.

Web crawling refers to the process of crawling web pages for the purpose of indexing them to support a search engine, as described in Deliverable 4.2. The survey aimed to gather opinions regarding specific aspects of the interactions of respondents with the web application. The aspects were categorized as follows:

- **Ease of use:** This section collected feedback on the usability of the SHERPA repository web application.
- **Navigation:** This section gathered users' opinions on the ease of navigation across the web application's pages.
- **Structure:** This section focused on users' views of the structure of the web application (i.e. the organisation of the content and information to which it provided access).
- **Relevance:** This section collected respondents' opinions on the relevance of the content and information stored in the data repository and accessed through the web application.
- **Layout and visuals:** This section covered the layout aspects of the web applications and the attractiveness of the visual elements used.
- **Search:** The last part of the evaluation survey addressed the search function within the web application including its usability, relevance, and accuracy of the search results, as well as any issues related to displaying the search results.

Each section included standard questions with the option of a five-point scale from 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree' and open-ended questions. The respondents were also asked to provide final remarks at the last chapter of the survey. An overview of the survey is shown in Annex 2.

Analysis of the responses was carried out and, where appropriate, changes were made to the repository and web crawler. A unique number was assigned to each free-text comment and classified as a short, medium, or long-term issue. Subsequently, the necessary actions were taken to address them. An overview of the survey results can be found in Annex 3 of the document.

4.2. Update and upgrade of the SHERPA online repository during the project's lifetime

Based on the validation of the survey and the action points defined with the partners involved in Task 4.3, the technical work to update and upgrade the platform was carried out.

The changes identified relate to navigation and loading speed when working with the repository, and the sorting and filtering options for projects, topics and keywords. A user-friendly solution was introduced to the web crawler to make it easier for non-technical users to configure topic searches and add new topics.

Besides the changes made in response to the feedback received, some other actions were taken, including a general update and improvement of the code of the platform to refine its functionalities and ensure its stability.

The platform's user interface had been updated to make it more attractive to users and to improve responsiveness on smaller devices. The User Manual on the platform was also updated.

In addition, the RURAL H2020 view has been added to showcase the four projects (DESIRA, MOVING, POLIRURAL, RURALIZATION) that, along with SHERPA, constitute the RUR 1-2 cluster. An overview of these projects can be found in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Overview of the projects included in 'RURAL HORIZON 2020'

An interactive map was added to the landing page for the Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), which displays the sites of the Rural Cluster, featuring a filter for different thematic levels (Figure 2, section 2).

Another feature added to the platform is buttons that enable users to provide feedback on the SHERPA online repository and suggest news topics, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: SHERPA repository, field of new topic suggestions

4.3. Maintenance and upgrade of the SHERPA web crawler during the project's lifetime

The SHERPA web crawler needed upgrading after feedback from the internal survey, in addition to the technical changes already mentioned. Maintenance and upgrades will ensure the effectiveness, efficiency, and adaptability of the web crawler throughout the project's life cycle. Therefore, improvements should be made regarding the dropdown options, as identified during the evaluation process. It was noted that specific options, including the names of the participants (universities, institutions, etc.) involved in the projects, were vulnerable to formatting errors. To address this problem, a pre-processing step was implemented to ensure a uniform format before loading participant names. Apart from the above, further revisions were necessary based on the evaluation, namely the need to include new topics. For this purpose, the crawler had been redesigned to facilitate the inclusion of new topics more efficiently according to the needs of the MAPs. Specifically, the crawler solution allows new topics to be added easily. Users can incorporate text files containing keywords related to the desired topics, thereby avoiding the need to modify the source code. This accessible approach enables lay users to set up fresh topic searches without mandating technical support.

5. Longevity and sustainability of the SHERPA online repository

5.1. The importance of the longevity and sustainability of the online repository

It is crucial to consider the longevity and sustainability of the SHERPA online repository beyond the life of a project. It is important to ensure there is continued access to the information collated as many research and development projects rely on previously undertaken and published work. The discontinuation of an online repository after project completion poses risks of interrupting the research continuity and accessibility, verification, or expansion of the work to others. The repository's longevity ensures that its content can still be accessible and beneficial to others, in line with FAIR principles.

The repository preserves and ensures the longevity of valuable information, data, documentation and resources for the benefit of future generations, researchers and users. This helps to prevent the loss of data and ensures that it remains relevant to ongoing projects. Moreover, sustainability planning helps to prevent duplicating projects by reducing redundant work in repositories, thereby saving time, resources (infrastructure, human labour) and energy (carbon footprint). By reducing redundant work, a sustainable repository serves as a foundation for future projects.

The SHERPA online repository should ensure reliable, accessible, and well-preserved data for sustainable development, facilitating informed decision-making and policy formulation towards achieving relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs represent a set of global objectives aimed at addressing various social, economic and environmental challenges by 2030. The online repository can aid in knowledge transfer, collaboration, innovation, and raising awareness, all of which are crucial to addressing the complex challenges presented in the SDGs and building a sustainable future. Namely, the repository stores important information, data, documentation and resources to ensure their longevity for the benefit of future generations, researchers and users. This prevents the loss of data and ensures its relevance to ongoing projects.

The longevity of a repository guarantees that its content remains accessible and useful to others. Its availability should contribute to achieving SDG 4 (Quality Education) through the educational resources it offers such as through the results of projects published.

The repository also contributes to SDG9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) promotion of innovation by sharing research, technological advancements, and best practices, in turn contributing to the development of sustainable infrastructure.

The content of the repository has direct relevance for the science, practice and policies of some SDGs. For example, the SHERPA MAP topics of 'Climate change and environmental services' and Climate Change and Land Use are relevant to SDG 12 'Responsible Consumption and Production', and SDG 13 'Climate Action'. The observations made in Section 5.1 about energy demand for IT infrastructure, links the need for the repository to be environmentally efficient and reduce exacerbating climate change through irresponsible consumption.

Furthermore, the repository is designed to reach different types of end users, in line with SDG 17 'Partnerships for the Goals' and its encouragement of partnerships between governments, organisations and communities.

5.2. Towards a sustainability plan for the SHERPA online repository

The final aspect of the project focuses on the ongoing sustainability of both the SHERPA repository and the web crawler. To ensure the continued existence of the platform and the provision of services after its

completion, certain factors need to be examined. This objective is important to the consortium and to the end-users.

During the SHERPA conference in January of 2022, the results of a survey run by SHERPA to assess the level of demand for MAPs to continue in some form after the end of the project were presented. Shared among the SHERPA MAPs, the survey received 199 responses. The results show that over 70% of participants were in favour of continuing the MAPs after SHERPA and a similar percentage would be interested in continuing to participate in the MAPs.

In the context of ensuring the sustainability of the web crawler, consideration was given to its potential reuse in other projects. The crawler has been used in the [Oper8](#) project's top-down approach, which involves obtaining and analyzing data from the CORDIS and EIP AGRI databases. This initiative has the specific objective of performing a systematic review centred on alternative weed control methods.

The Figure below provides an overview of a SWOT analysis regarding the sustainability and longevity of the SHERPA MAPs.

Figure 11: SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)

Directions towards a strategic plan for the sustainability of the SHERPA online repository are presented in detail below.

- **Strengths**

In this dimension, we consider the advantages of the project, such as the internal resources (know-how, technology, motivations) that will help to meet the requirements and avoid the threats. In our case, we have an established knowledge base and innovation, as the web crawler was developed specifically for this project. Furthermore, the use of the Repository is user-friendly, with information accessible by means of a limited number of steps, and filters available to manage the number of results returned from the repository. It provides content of public interest users (scientists, researchers, policy

makers, representatives of civil society organisations, public administrations and authorities, citizens) who can benefit from the information available in the Repository.

- **Weaknesses**

- Internal weaknesses are defined as deficiencies on service provision, including quality control problems, changes in user behaviour and technological vulnerabilities. Another potential weakness for sustainability is funding, which may be compromised if the repository relies heavily on external sources of funding that may change over time

- **Opportunities**

Opportunities are external situations or trends that create favourable conditions for an organisation's (or project's) specialised skills. For the repository, these include local, national and international events that increase popularity, technological changes that benefit services, and changing social patterns or demographics. The impact of public policy can create opportunities for the repository in informing rural development policy and gaining support from government bodies. An example of such an opportunity is the inclusion and link to the repository home page from the webpage on the European Union Rural Action Plan Stronger pillar in relation to [Creating a stronger innovation ecosystem for rural areas](#). Opportunities will also be aided by partnerships collaborations with universities, research institutions and rural development organisations to broaden content and funding sources.

- **Threats**

Threats refer to external factors or trends that could negatively affect the demand for an organisation's (or project's) expertise. In our case, the risk is that the expectations of individuals will not be met throughout the life of the project. If user engagement remains low, there will be challenges of attracting new content and users, potentially endangering the repository's sustainability. Additionally, financial constraints, such as economic downturns or funding cuts, may pose a further threat.

7.1 5.2.1 Repository maintenance costs

Staff salaries are required to cover software developers, scientific coordinators and support staff. The general creation and maintenance of the website is carried out by web developers. They are responsible for the overall appearance and responsiveness of a website and manage its technical aspects such as speed and capacity. The web developer will be responsible for maintaining the software/infrastructure and the web crawler within the SHERPA project. As the web crawler searches for information from databases such as CORDIS, which may change and be updated throughout the life of the project, it requires regular adjustments.

Future users of the repository should still be able to suggest new topics. In turn these require to be evaluated by repository manager the costs of whom require to be funded. The manager has to evaluate the topics for their relevance, assess the keywords entered by users, and search and post projects related to the respective topics.

The support staff have the responsibility of connecting the work between the scientific coordinator and the developer. As such, this person should communicate with the developer to 'run' the web crawler based on the suggested keywords and to search CORDIS and other databases, so that an evaluation of the results that 'return' at an initial stage can be performed.

Indicative costs for the operation and maintenance of the SHERPA repository at its current level of service may include personnel costs (software developer: €4,050, scientific coordinator: €4,637, support staff: €2,458 per month) as well as monthly maintenance costs of €148 for infrastructure operation and maintenance. This is only an estimate, but costs may rise due to changes in the repository team's circumstances (e.g. promotions, salary increases), and future investments may be enabled.

As the SHERPA project will end on 30 September 2023, it should be considered to continue the results of this project in terms of its sustainability, such as practice abstracts, discussions and position papers. A feasible solution at this stage seems to be to host these results in other platforms. A solution for this purpose seems to be [the EU-FarmBook project](#), which started in August 2022 and will last for 7 years. More specifically, in the EU-FarmBook project, 29 EU partner organisations are working on the creation of a [Europe-wide digital platform](#) for the collection and sharing of agricultural and forestry knowledge. The idea is to bring together the tangible results of EU-funded research and innovation projects on a user-friendly platform and provide a useful and effective tool for farmers, foresters and advisors across Europe. At the time of writing, there is a pilot version of this platform. The external release will be in February 2024. The Agricultural University of Athens is involved in this project as a Work Package Leader related to the development of the platform. This means that the connection with this project would be direct.

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6. Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: Projects available per topic

Projects added in 2020.

Acronym	Topic
PLUREL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BioVill	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DARDRA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LANDSUPPORT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MARSUPIA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
POLELUC	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PRIMA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LUPUS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ATLAS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TURAS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
FARMING ECONOMICALLY	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ROBUST	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TOP-MARD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
QUING	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DomEQUAL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MUSE GRIDS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
FEMAGREE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RurInno	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURALIMAGINATIONS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EWTEK	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RELOCAL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MEMOLA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

UNISECO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AGFORWARD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ENVIEVAL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ARANGE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
REFORLAN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AGRINERGY	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ERA-ARD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LUMOCAP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SPEAR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MULTAGRI	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DeltaScan	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ECMO-BIOMARKER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ATTAVIK	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIVERUR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TUCAN3G	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
WETPaC	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
A-BARD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SARDANA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SmartRuralGrid	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
NB4WASTE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BE-Rural	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Smartmushroom	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BIOEASTSUP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SCREEN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MICROFUEL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

AgroCycle	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SOLINSA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Diverfarming	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
GO-GRASS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RUBIZMO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CAPTIVATE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
POWER4BIO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CoPs	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Dendromass4Europe	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SMARTPROTECT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
GROW GREEN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
OPERAS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TERESA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AfricanBioServices	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ALARM	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BIR AL-NAS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ESMERALDA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CONSOLE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EFFECT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DataBio	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EMME-CARE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURAL DECISIONS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MEDRES	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ADAGIO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
FUME	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

WATER4CROPS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BIOECOSIM	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
INTELLICORR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SASSPO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TeRRIFICA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
WATERPROTECT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CAP-IRE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DERREG	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
STEP-IN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AIM-AP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CD-LINKS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SmartCultTour	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURITAGE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
GILDED	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
NEXTFOOD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIAISON	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SGRANGE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TWISTER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ETUDE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
YOUNG FARMERS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RAPIDO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AGRUMIG	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
NEWBIE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURALIZATION	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURALJOBS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

MATILDA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
USES	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ThinkNature	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PATH	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PROTEAN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Polirural	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ECO-BROKER	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features through landscape features
CLIMB	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PlantSoilGradients	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features through landscape features
PERCEIVE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PAVITR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
URBAG	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ECOPOTENTIAL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SARMENTI	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
E-LAND	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ORTIKA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BIOSCENE 2019	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Legumes Translated	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
HIVEOPOLIS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PAINLESS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
REACH	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
GLOBESCAPE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

ADAFARM	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
EcoStack	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
HyPhOE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
Ecol of interactions	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SUPER-G	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Target-N2O	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
EXTINCT	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
MeeLIH	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
TRITRONITRO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Mobile-Age	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EARNEST	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
CHOCOLATE4LIFE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
FFSize	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Circular Agronomics	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ConHuB	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
COASTAL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ROSEWOOD	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EPIDIVERSE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
Go SIV	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
GREENPATROL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DIAGRASS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
HOPE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
RE-mapping	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

FeedSax	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CIRCASA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
DarkMix	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RURACTION	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
VineScout	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Ground Truth 2.0	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
FTI Cocoon	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LANDSENSE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
NoAW	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
DECISIVE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SnowRESolution	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
WATLY	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
HNV-Link	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SIZE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
RAPSODY	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
HOOKaWORM	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
INSPIRATION	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Symbiosis	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SIMRA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CommBeBiz	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BAG-FS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SteamBio	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
IMPRESS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
GRAGE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

ADD ME!	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ERMES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PAENCE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
LANDMARK	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
FORESTA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ECOAQUA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
CAERUS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PEGASUS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SIGMA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SMARTOPENDATA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BIFFIO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
HERCULES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
WHEALBI	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
HYDROREEF	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
MEDCHANGE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
UNDERINDIA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
FORCONEPAL	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
NO-WASTE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
IASIMOV	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
FOODMETRES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
CASTLE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
LOGISTEC	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SoilWasteBenefits	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features

GLOBEPURE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
AGRI-ECO SERVICES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
RECOMPRA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
MASELTOV	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
RODAM	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
CANTOGETHER	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
COCONET	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
TEEMBIO	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ABSTRESS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
INTEREST	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
STAR-AGROENERGY	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
COMBIOSERVE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
EARLYHUMANIMPACT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SedSRes	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PURE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
DEMARN	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
KODKOD	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
BIOALGAESORB	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
CORE ORGANIC II	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
LANDSCAPEPARTNERS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
LEGUME-FUTURES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
EFH-GIS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features

GLOGENDER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ECOLIVA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SCALES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SPATIODIVERSITY	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
FUNCTREE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
BIOCONNECTENCE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ARCTIC ENDOPHYTES	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
MOBITAG	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
RUFUS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PROTECT CROP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
HUNT	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
APODYNA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
4F CROPS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ACQWA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SWUP-MED	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ANAEE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SPECIFICITY	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
EULAFF	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
INTASÁ 2005-104-7647	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
TRACES	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
COMPETE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
BIWACLIM	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features

CARPENVCHANGE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SEACASE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
GEO-BENE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
LANDSCAPE BIRDS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ASPECT	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ACACIAGUM	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
GRASSLAND	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PHILMINAQ	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
WAFLA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
KITE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
MODLAIT	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
DRYLAND RESEARCH SSA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
INCOFISH	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
GENFUNDIV	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ELMAA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SEAMLESS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
PASARELAS	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
GLOCHAMORE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
RES INTEGRATION	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
IPDEV	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
MEA-SCOPE	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features

INSEA	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
FISH CONDITION	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
ECOLECONMOD	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
TURPRO	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
WATERTOOL	Rural Policies to protect and enhance Biodiversity through landscape features
SUSTAIN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Waste air treatment	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
The Autonomous Office	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Enrich a poor waste	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ENERING	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE HelpSoil	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Life PREFER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LifeHYGENet	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE REUSING POSIDONIA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Eucalyptus Energy	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE COGENERATION PL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
EcoLife	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
life	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE STARS (+20)	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE ReWaCo	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFEZEROSTORE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE MIX_FERTILIZER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFENaturEtrade	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Housing Landscapes	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SANEPLAN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

LIFE+ REWIND	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SMART Hospital	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
SMAPUDE_LIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SynSpirIt	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE MEMORY	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
QUARTERBACK for LIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Coop 2020	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE+ small scale CHP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE REGENERA LIMIA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
WISER LIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE PERSUADED	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE OxyUp	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE WaterLIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE FACTORY MICROGRID	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE_OPERE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SAMCIP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE TEXTILEATHER	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SIAMEC	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE URBAN	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE BATTLE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE DEMOWAVE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE VINEYARDS4HEAT (V4H)	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

LIFE LINES	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE GYM	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
Maopolska Region	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE+ POLYFARMING	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
BG4US LIFE 2015	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE BITMAPS	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE AGRI ADAPT	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Clinomics	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
ECOELECTRICITY LIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE HEATLAND	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
PREPAIR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFECAB	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE AMYBEAR	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE BooGI	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE SOLIEVA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE Waste2NeoAlginate	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE_PHIPP	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE ASTI	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE AGUA DE PRATA	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
AlgaeService for LIFE	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE GreenPower	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas
LIFE_WZROST_PL	Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas

Projects added in 2021.

Acronym	Topic
REFERTIL	Climate change and environmental sustainability
FUNCTREE	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SMARTSOIL	Climate change and environmental sustainability
CLIMSAVE	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SOLINSA	Climate change and environmental sustainability
BE-Rural	Climate change and environmental sustainability
GenRes Bridge	Climate change and environmental sustainability
EO4AGRI	Climate change and environmental sustainability
OPERAS	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SuWaNu Europe	Climate change and environmental sustainability
AGFORWARD	Climate change and environmental sustainability
TeRRIFICA	Climate change and environmental sustainability
OPERANDUM	Climate change and environmental sustainability
DRAGON	Climate change and environmental sustainability
Phusicos	Climate change and environmental sustainability
ROSEWOOD	Climate change and environmental sustainability
LIAISON	Climate change and environmental sustainability
UNISECO	Climate change and environmental sustainability
RURITAGE	Climate change and environmental sustainability

LIFT	Climate change and environmental sustainability
Minland	Climate change and environmental sustainability
COASTAL	Climate change and environmental sustainability
LANDSUPPORT	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SUPREMA	Climate change and environmental sustainability
RUBIZMO	Climate change and environmental sustainability
LIVERUR	Climate change and environmental sustainability
NEFERTITI	Climate change and environmental sustainability
eForFuel	Climate change and environmental sustainability
NAIAD	Climate change and environmental sustainability
Smart-AKIS	Climate change and environmental sustainability
FOWARIM	Climate change and environmental sustainability
ClimeFish	Climate change and environmental sustainability
ISAGE	Climate change and environmental sustainability
Diverfarming	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SIMRA	Climate change and environmental sustainability
HNV-Link	Climate change and environmental sustainability
DiverIMPACTS	Climate change and environmental sustainability
SURE-Farm	Climate change and environmental sustainability
ISQAPER	Climate change and environmental sustainability
LANDMARK	Climate change and environmental sustainability

AgroCycle	Climate change and environmental sustainability
FATIMA	Climate change and environmental sustainability
LANDSENSE	Climate change and environmental sustainability
GROW	Climate change and environmental sustainability
EMPHASIS	Climate change and environmental sustainability
FLOWERED	Climate change and environmental sustainability
MOSES	Climate change and environmental sustainability
Rural Riches	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PARSEC	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
LOTUS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
BE-Rural	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RichWater	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PROVIDE	Climate change and environmental sustainability
PAVITR	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Diverfarming	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
LEGVALUE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RurInno	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
BioVill	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PerformFISH	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
DiverIMPACTS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
InnovAfrica	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy

CAPSELLA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
BABET-REALS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SYSTEMIC	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
WAZIUP	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
AgriLink	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
CYBELE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
ECO-LOGIC GREEN FARM	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
FAIRshare	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
GenRes Bridge	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
INNOLABS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
NEPTUNE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SuWaNu Europe	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
COALA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
ECOFISH	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Transnational Localism	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SENSAGRI	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Minland	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RURITAGE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
CERERE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
AGROinLOG	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PoshBee	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy

SMARTCHAIN	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
LIAISON	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
UNISECO	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SHui	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SheepNet	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RURACTION	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Inno4Grass	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PROIntensAfrica	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Circular Agronomics	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RUBIZMO	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
greenGain	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
RUC-APS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
MAPS-LED	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SteamBio	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
ROSEWOOD	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
CLIC	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SANSA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
NADIRA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
Newcotiana	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
INNOQUA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
ESMERALDA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy

SIEUGreen	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
AgroCycle	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
PANACEA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
EDEN ISS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
TEMPO	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
POnte	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SUPURBFOOD	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
LANDSENSE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SWAMP	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
DIVERSIFOOD	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
CANTOGETHER	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
VALERIE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
WASTE2FUELS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
FOWARIM	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
COEXIST	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
CLAFIS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
REFERTIL	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
GRASSMARGINS	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
FUNCITREE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
KNEU	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
SOLINSA	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy

TREES4FUTURE	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy
COCONET	Changing in production and diversification of the rural economy

Projects added in 2022.

Acronym	Topic
WAZIUP	Digitalisation in rural areas
TEKNOAX 2.0	Digitalisation in rural areas
CAPTIVATE	Digitalisation in rural areas
One-Flow	Digitalisation in rural areas
BESMART	Digitalisation in rural areas
SUFISA	Digitalisation in rural areas
AgriLink	Digitalisation in rural areas
greenGain	Digitalisation in rural areas
Smart-AKIS	Digitalisation in rural areas
InnovAfrica	Digitalisation in rural areas
BIOrescue	Digitalisation in rural areas
GROW	Digitalisation in rural areas
ROSEWOOD	Digitalisation in rural areas
AgroCycle	Digitalisation in rural areas
PJ05 Remote Tower	Digitalisation in rural areas
GATES	Digitalisation in rural areas

INCREDible	Digitalisation in rural areas
SWAMP	Digitalisation in rural areas
SLIPO	Digitalisation in rural areas
LiveSEN	Digitalisation in rural areas
ECO-BROKER	Digitalisation in rural areas
RUBIZMO	Digitalisation in rural areas
DataBio	Digitalisation in rural areas
NEPTUNE	Digitalisation in rural areas
STARGATE	Digitalisation in rural areas
AGRICORE	Digitalisation in rural areas
LIAISON	Digitalisation in rural areas
LANDSUPPORT	Digitalisation in rural areas
MIND STEP	Digitalisation in rural areas
iPollinate	Digitalisation in rural areas
TMate	Digitalisation in rural areas
AFarCloud	Digitalisation in rural areas
SOMIRO	Digitalisation in rural areas
MENLAOS_NT	Digitalisation in rural areas
WIRE2018	Digitalisation in rural areas
DRAGON	Digitalisation in rural areas
DEMETER	Digitalisation in rural areas

SmartCulTour	Digitalisation in rural areas
Hive Pro	Digitalisation in rural areas
Legumes Translated	Digitalisation in rural areas
ATLAS	Digitalisation in rural areas
AURORAL	Digitalisation in rural areas
PRYSTINE	Digitalisation in rural areas
AGTECH	Digitalisation in rural areas
YOUNG FARMERS	Digitalisation in rural areas
SARMENTI	Digitalisation in rural areas
OB-VISLY	Digitalisation in rural areas
EPES	Digitalisation in rural areas
MOSAIC 2B	Digitalisation in rural areas
MOBITAG	Digitalisation in rural areas
dRural	Digitalisation in rural areas
FUTUREFARM	Digitalisation in rural areas
CO-FREE	Digitalisation in rural areas
DESIRA	Digitalisation in rural areas
CYBELE	Digitalisation in rural areas
TEKNOAX 2.0	Climate change and land use
EO4AGRI	Digitalisation in rural areas
ROBUST	Digitalisation in rural areas

CAPELLA	Climate change and land use
INMOST	Climate change and land use
PEGASUS	Climate change and land use
RURECO	Climate change and land use
EDU-DEM	Climate change and land use
LANDMARK	Climate change and land use
FATIMA	Climate change and land use
SWATCH	Climate change and land use
SMARTLAW	Climate change and land use
PAST	Climate change and land use
greenGain	Climate change and land use
DiverIMPACTS	Climate change and land use
ISQAPER	Climate change and land use
Diverfarming	Climate change and land use
GROW	Climate change and land use
HOOKaWORM	Climate change and land use
GREENPATROL	Climate change and land use
AgroCycle	Climate change and land use
Ground Truth 2.0	Climate change and land use
INCLUDE	Climate change and land use
RUC-APS	Climate change and land use

PROVIDE	Climate change and land use
MarTERA	Climate change and land use
RURACTION	Climate change and land use
INCREdible	Climate change and land use
AGROInLOG	Climate change and land use
ECO-BROKER	Climate change and land use
ANTHEA	Climate change and land use
CONEXUS	Climate change and land use
CARE4C	Climate change and land use
FutureMARES	Climate change and land use
RUBIZMO	Climate change and land use
AGROMIX	Climate change and land use
CroBio2020	Climate change and land use
MODFaBe	Climate change and land use
NEPTUNE	Climate change and land use
Contracts2.0	Climate change and land use
BE-Rural	Climate change and land use
WATERAGRI	Climate change and land use
CONSOLE	Climate change and land use
AURORA	Climate change and land use
MERLIN	Climate change and land use

I-CISK	Climate change and land use
SHui	Climate change and land use
LANDSUPPORT	Climate change and land use
REFLECT AFRICA	Climate change and land use
SUPER-G	Climate change and land use
AGRICORE	Climate change and land use
PoIRural	Climate change and land use
LIFT	Climate change and land use
4F CROPS	Climate change and land use
BESTMAP	Climate change and land use
PASHMINA	Climate change and land use
AGRIC-LASERUAV	Climate change and land use
RURITAGE	Climate change and land use
HUNT	Climate change and land use
CCTAME	Climate change and land use
VIVACE	Climate change and land use
CAPRI-RD	Climate change and land use
SIRIUS	Climate change and land use
SOLINSA	Climate change and land use
PHENOTYPE	Climate change and land use
CLARIS LPB	Climate change and land use

FORESTERRA	Climate change and land use
PROFICIENCY	Climate change and land use
TREUEVALUE	Climate change and land use
NexGenAgriChem	Climate change and land use
COMBIOSERVE	Climate change and land use
CASTLE	Climate change and land use
POLELUC	Climate change and land use
STAR TREE	Climate change and land use
ANAEE	Climate change and land use
IMPACT2C	Climate change and land use
RURALIZATION	Climate change and land use
QUESSA	Climate change and land use
ROBUST	Climate change and land use
HERCULES	Climate change and land use
RE-mapping	Social dimension of rural areas
IMPRESS	Social dimension of rural areas
HNV-Link	Social dimension of rural areas
Smart-AKIS	Social dimension of rural areas
InnovAfrica	Social dimension of rural areas
LT2016	Social dimension of rural areas
LIGHTS Nights	Social dimension of rural areas

DomEQUAL	Social dimension of rural areas
CONEXUS	Social dimension of rural areas
ECO-BROKER	Social dimension of rural areas
VARCITIES	Social dimension of rural areas
ROMI	Social dimension of rural areas
Go SIV	Social dimension of rural areas
MigRural	Social dimension of rural areas
NEWBIE	Social dimension of rural areas
INCLUSION	Social dimension of rural areas
SIMRA	Social dimension of rural areas
EFFECT	Social dimension of rural areas
PROVIDE	Social dimension of rural areas
CONSOLE	Social dimension of rural areas
STEP-IN	Social dimension of rural areas
Ground Truth 2.0	Social dimension of rural areas
LIFT	Social dimension of rural areas
SUPER-G	Social dimension of rural areas
AURORA	Social dimension of rural areas
RURALIZATION	Social dimension of rural areas
HES-GEO	Social dimension of rural areas
UNISECO	Social dimension of rural areas

TRANSNATIONAL	Social dimension of rural areas
HYSOTIB	Social dimension of rural areas
ReROOT	Social dimension of rural areas
datarev	Social dimension of rural areas
RURITAGE	Social dimension of rural areas
AURORAL	Social dimension of rural areas
SUSTAINFORESTS	Social dimension of rural areas
TRACTION	Social dimension of rural areas
SURDIM	Social dimension of rural areas
YOUNG FARMERS	Social dimension of rural areas
FUTURES 2021	Social dimension of rural areas
PASHMINA	Social dimension of rural areas
RURBANAFRICA	Social dimension of rural areas
CLAIM	Social dimension of rural areas
LANDGRABRU	Social dimension of rural areas
GOVERN	Social dimension of rural areas
PHENOTYPE	Social dimension of rural areas
POLELUC	Social dimension of rural areas
LIPSE	Social dimension of rural areas
RurInno	Social dimension of rural areas
PoliRural	Social dimension of rural areas

RURALJOBS	Social dimension of rural areas
DESIRA	Social dimension of rural areas
MATILDE	Social dimension of rural areas
FARMWELL	Social dimension of rural areas
Whole-COMM	Social dimension of rural areas
WelcomingSpaces	Social dimension of rural areas
RurInno	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
TEKNOAX 2.0	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
IMAJINE	Social dimension of rural areas
FOWARIM	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
WASTE2FUELS	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SIMRA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
TRADITOM	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CAPTIVATE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SUFISA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SMART2D	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
ISQAPER	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
BioHorizon	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SoIACE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CommBeBiz	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
greenGain	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

DiverIMPACTS	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
DIVERSify	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
PerformFISH	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Symbiosis	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Repower Democracy	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Diverfarming	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Dendromass4Europe	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SafeWaterAfrica	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
InterAccent	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
AgroCycle	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
INCLUSION	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SWAMP	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
PROVIDE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
NEWBIE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
ROSEWOOD	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
RURACTION	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
AGROinLOG	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
INCREDible	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Scaling up Novihum	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Eu PIG	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
NEFERTITI	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

LiveSEN	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
ECO-BROKER	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
RUBIZMO	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SustInAfrica	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
INNOLABS	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
HPC4E	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
EFFECT	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Contracts2.0	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
STARGATE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LIVERUR	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
BE-Rural	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
FOODLAND	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LOTUS	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CONSOLE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LANDSUPPORT	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SHui	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LIFT	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
I-CISK	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LIAISON	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SMARTCHAIN	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
ENERGICA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

HES-GEO	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
AFarCloud	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Transition2BIO	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
BRANCHES	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
DEMETER	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
FARMWELL	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
DRAGON	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
datarev	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
BASAJAUN	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Legumes Translated	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Hive Pro	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CELISE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SmartCulTour	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
DELTAdev	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
VERVE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
WelfareStruggles	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
BIO4AFRICA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
TeRRIFICA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CYBELE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SPARD	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SUSTAINMED	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

INSTAPA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
DERREG	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SOLINSA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
COCONET	Climate change and land use
SOLIBAM	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
FORESTERRA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CLAIM	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
RURBANAFRICA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CO-FREE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
EAU4FOOD	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
MOSAIC 2B	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
PURE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
EVOSYSBIO	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SUPURBFOOD	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
HERCULES	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
LIPSE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
STAR TREE	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
AGFORWARD	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SKIN	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SUSFOOD2	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
SIMBA	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

PEGASUS	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
CIRCLES	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
MOVING	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
FOX	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
MAGIC	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
ROBUST	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
Strength2Food	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains
COCONET	Towards sustainable and resilient value chains

Projects added in 2023.

Acronym	Topic
RURECO	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
DYNAVERSITY	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
DomEQUAL	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
MAPS-LED	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
greenGain	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
SmartAgriHubs	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
BioVill	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
SIMRA	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
LANDSUPPORT	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
SmartCulTour	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
Farmers Pride	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
Repower Democracy	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
BE-Rural	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
AGRUMIG	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
ROBUST	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
SMARTCHAIN	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
CONSOLE	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
GLOBESCAPE	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
CLIC	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes

EFFECT	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
Transition2BIO	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
BESTMAP	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
RURAGRI	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
FoodSHIFT2030	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
CONEXUS	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
MATILDE	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
Phusicos	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes
SHERPA	Empowering rural areas in multi-level governance processes

6.2 Annex 2: SHERPA online repository evaluation survey

The survey items

Ease-of-use

- Q1: I find the web application easy to use.
- Q2: The web application takes too long to load.
- Q3: Did you face any difficulties using the web application? Can you describe them? (open question)

Navigation

- Q1: It was easy for me to navigate through the pages of the web application (e.g. get back to the previous page or visit another one).
- Q2: It was easy and obvious for me to know my position in the web application at any given moment.
- Q3: The labels used in the web application's main menu are indicative of the pages I was able to visit.
- Q4: When clicking on a link, I was able to get access to a page of the web application that contained the content and information I was expecting to find.
- Q5: Are there any comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the navigation elements/labels used in the web application or any inconsistencies you noticed? (For example, a broken link, a label not so obvious or explanatory, not obvious or non-responsive buttons or links). (open question)

Structure

- Q1: The structure of the web application is easily understood and clear.
- Q2: It is clear what is the page that I need to go to in order to find the desired information.
- Q3: Are there any comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the web application's structure? (open question)

Relevance

- Q1: The content and information is useful to all the target user categories (e.g. representatives of the consortium, MAP members, representatives of other projects, citizens, researchers, policy makers, etc.).
- Q2: The content and information is sufficient to all the target user categories (e.g. representatives of the consortium, MAP members, representatives of other projects, citizens, researchers, policy makers, etc.).
- Q3: Are there any other/additional pieces of information that you would like to have access to? (open question)
- Q4: When using the web application, I sometimes get overwhelmed with the information provided.
- Q5: Are there any specific pages in which less information should be provided? (open question)

Layout and visuals

- Q1: I find the design of the web application appealing.
- Q2: The visual elements used detract my attention from the content and information delivered through the web application.
- Q3: I find the web application's layout consistent with the project's official website in terms of the visual elements used (colours, graphics, font style, etc.).
- Q4: Are there any other comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the layout and visuals in the web application? (open question)

Search

- Q1: Using the search box to search for projects related to a rural topic, by typing in search terms of my preference, is easy and intuitive.
- Q2: The display of search results makes it easy to spot the information I want.
- Q3: When executing a search operation in the web application, I get the results I was expecting for.
- Q4: The options provided for sorting the results of a search operation are useful.
- Q5: Are there any other options that should be considered for sorting the project results? (open question)
- Q6: Would you delete an option for sorting the project results?
- Q7: The filters made available to narrow down the number of search results in the list of projects are easy to understand and use.
- Q8: The values per filter help to make a more specific selection and narrow down the number of search results presented.
- Q9: I find the option to combine multiple values per filter or more than one filters helpful when it comes to narrowing down the number of search results.
- Q10: Are there any other comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the search function provided in the web application? (open question)

6.3 Annex 3: Results of the SHERPA online repository evaluation survey

This Annex contains the questions and the answers provided in the prototype web application for accessing the SHERPA online repository.

Ease-of-use Question #1

I find the web application easy to use.
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
From the responses provided with regard to how easy the use of the web application is, it can be said that, in general terms, the evaluators have found it easy to use (there is one neutral response).

Ease-of-use Question #2

The web application takes too long to load.
6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided in respect to **whether the application takes too long to load**, it has been **unanimously reported that the application does not take (too) long to load**.

Ease-of-use Question #3 (open question)

Did you face any difficulties using the web application? Can you describe them?

- When clicking on a project, it directs me to the European website. Then, only when I press the [previous button](#) I can access to the project page on the repository.
 - My suggestion would be to include the "rural topics" directly on the home page, or at least include a button on the homepage (other than the Main Menu) to find the Rural Topics from there.
 - No problems with use, but some issues with elements in the interface. See later comment and email.
 - When clicking on the title of a project it goes directly on the EU CORDIS website, while, by clicking on the box it stays on the sherpa website. Maybe could be a good idea to specify the presence of the external link to EU CORDIS by including "external link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/777137>".

Navigation Question #1

It was easy for me to navigate through the pages of the web application (e.g. get back to the previous page or visit another one).
6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether it has been easy to navigate through the pages of the web application**, it can be said that **mixed feelings have been received**. Half of the responses provided are positive, whereas the other half of them are negative.

Navigation Question #2

It was easy and obvious for me to know my position in the web application at any given moment.
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
From the responses provided with regard to **whether it has been easy for someone to know his/her position in the web application at any given moment**, it has been found that half of the responses provided are positive and the other half of the responses are either negative or neutral.
Based on this feedback, we can say that **more concrete navigation elements** need to be made available in order to make the **identification of the current position** in the application **more obvious**.

Navigation Question #3

The labels used in the web application's main menu are indicative of the pages I am able to visit.
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
From the responses provided with regard to **whether the labels used in the main menu provide adequate indications of the pages that can be visited**, it has been found that there is an **absolute diversity** in the responses provided.
We **need to dive deeper into our respondents' insights** and **seek some further and detailed feedback** in order to find out what the actual situation is here.

Navigation Question #4

When clicking on a link, I was able to get access to a page of the web application that contained the content and information I was expecting to find.
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
From the responses provided with regard to **whether it has been feasible to get directed to application page expected when clicking on a link**, it has been found that **this goal has been almost achieved** (as indicated by most of the responses, which are positive).

Navigation

Question #5 (open question)

Are there any comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the navigation elements/labels used in the web application or any inconsistencies you noticed? (for example, a broken link, a label not so obvious or explanatory, not obvious or non-responsive buttons or links).

- The landing page should be the topics. And maybe the link to the main sherpa website should not be as another tab because it leads to somewhere else than the repository. Making a hyperlink on the sherpa logo maybe?
- I would change the name of "SHERPA OFFICIAL" to "SHERPA WEBSITE", as it is not clear what "official" means. When searching in any of the rural topics, it is not possible to go back unless clicking in the main menu. Maybe it would be useful to have an option to go back to rural topics in the breadcrumbs (Selected Rural Topic > Long-Term Vision).
- Some dropdown options need to be improved - some details to be corrected, but links seem to work.
- I would add "external link: (link to the EU CORDIS WEBSITE)" because it is not clear that by clicking the title of a project it brings you to the source. For the navigation, I would include the hierarchy of the pages: if I am on the page of a specific projectxyz, I would like to have on the top of the page something like: sherpa repository > rural topics > projectxyz. This way it will be clear which level I am visiting and would allow me to go back and decide on which level of detail I want to go next.

Structure

Question #1

The structure of the web application is easily understood and clear.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

Except for two responses that express a neutral position (i.e. one third of the responses provided in total), the majority of the responses (66.7%) to the question about whether the structure of the application is clear and easy to understand, indicate a positive feedback. Yet, we need to keep the neutral responses in mind.

Structure

Question #2

It is clear what is the page that I need to go to in order to find the desired information.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to whether it is clear what page needs to be visited in order to get the desired information, it has been found that there is a great diversity in the responses provided.

We need to dive deeper into our respondents' insights and seek some further and detailed feedback in order to find out what the actual situation is here.

Structure

Question #3 (open question)

Are there any comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the web application's structure?

- Similar comments like those previously provided.
- See first answer: I would include the access to rural topics also in the home page. I would also include somewhere a description of the filters available (e.g. subtopics vs keywords).
- No response.
- Maybe have a direct link/button to previous & ongoing Project, i.e. not going via the Rural Topics button.
- I couldn't find a link to Sherpa Position & Discussion Papers => maybe this is still coming?
- Maybe add rename "Rural Topics" with "Rural Topics by Sherpa" or "Sherpa Topics".

Relevance

Question #1

The content and information is useful to all the target user categories (e.g. representatives of the consortium, MAP members, representatives of other ...ects, citizens, researchers, policy makers, etc.).
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
 From the responses provided with regard to **whether the content and information provided is useful to all the target user categories**, it has been found that, in general terms, **the feedback provided is positive** (the three quarters of the responses lean towards this direction) with **only one response being neutral** (16.7% of the total responses provided) **and another one stating a disagreement** to the specific position.

Relevance

Question #2

The content and information is sufficient to all the target user categories (e.g. representatives of the consortium, MAP members, representatives of ot...ects, citizens, researchers, policy makers, etc.).
6 responses

Rating scale used...
1: Completely disagree
2: Disagree
3: Neither agree nor disagree
4: Agree
5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
 From the responses provided with regard to **whether the content and information provided is sufficient to all the target user categories**, it is evident that, in general terms, a **positive feedback** has been **made available** (apart from one response stating a neutral position).

Relevance

Question #3 (open question)

Are there any other/additional pieces of information that you would like to have access to?

- A map with countries highlighted instead of the acronym of countries.
- Hyperlinks to partners in a box at the top right corner for each project.

Relevance

Question #4

When using the web application, I sometimes get overwhelmed with the information provided.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether the user gets overwhelmed with the information provided**, it appears there is a **spread in the points** made by the responses provided. The **negative and neutral responses** gathered constitute the **majority of the feedback**.

Relevance

Question #5 (open question)

Are there any specific pages in which less information should be provided?

- For the publications, only most relevant should appear, not all of them.
- No.

Layout and visuals

Question #1

I find the design of the web application appealing.

6 responses

Rating scale used...
 1: Completely disagree
 2: Disagree
 3: Neither agree nor disagree
 4: Agree
 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
 From the responses provided with regard to **whether the design of the application is appealing**, a **positive feedback has been unanimously provided** by the respondents.

Layout and visuals

Question #2

The visual elements used detract my attention from the content and information delivered through the web application.

6 responses

Rating scale used...
 1: Completely disagree
 2: Disagree
 3: Neither agree nor disagree
 4: Agree
 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
 From the responses provided with regard to **whether the visual elements employed function in a disruptive rather than facilitative way**, the **majority of the responses provided are negative** (at the rate of 83.3%) with only **one response** (equal to only 16.7% of the total responses provided) **stating a neutral position**.

Layout and visuals

Question #3

I find the web application's lay-out consistent with the project's official website in terms of the visual elements used (colours, graphics, font style, etc.).

6 responses

Rating scale used...
 1: Completely disagree
 2: Disagree
 3: Neither agree nor disagree
 4: Agree
 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided
 From the responses provided with regard to **whether the visual elements employed are consistent with the project's visual identity**, **all the responses provided are positive** (one third of the responses provided express an agreement and the other two thirds express a strong agreement).

Layout and visuals

Question #4 (open question)

Are there any other comments/suggestions that you would like to make with regard to the layout and visuals in the web application?

- Maps for the spatial extent of each project.
- None.

Search

Question #1

Using the search box to search for projects related to a rural topic, by typing in search terms of my preference, is easy and intuitive.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to whether the use of the search box has been easy and intuitive, most of the responses provided are positive (83.3% of the total number of responses provided). There is only one response (16.7% of the total number of responses) expressing a neutral position.

Search Question #2

The display of search results makes it easy to spot the information I want.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether it is easy to spot the information needed from the search results**, it appears that there is a **spread in the points made** by the responses provided. **One third of the responses are neutral and half of them are positive** (expressing either an agreement or strong agreement). There is also **one response** expressing a **negative statement**.

Remedial actions need to be taken.

Search Question #3

When executing a search operation in the web application, I get the results I was expecting for.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether the user gets the information expected from the execution of a search operation**, it appears that there is a **spread in the points made** by the responses provided. **Most responses are positive** (half of them), **one third of them** express a **neutral position**, and we also have **one disagreement** with this statement.

Remedial actions need to be taken.

Search Question #4

The options provided for sorting the results of a search operation are useful.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether the options made available for sorting the search results provided to the user**, what we can say is that **the overall feeling is positive** (more than three quarters of the respondents have provided a positive responses either in terms of expressing an agreement or a strong agreement). There is **only one neutral statement expressed**.

Search Question #5 (open question)

Are there any other options that should be considered for sorting the project results?

- Add sort by funding programme.
- Relevance for SHERPA consortium members/relevance for external.

Search Question #6

Would you delete an option for sorting the project results?

4 responses

Search Question #7

The filters made available to narrow down the number of search results in the list of projects are easy to understand and use.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether the filters are easy to understand and use**, what we can say is that **the overall feeling is positive** (more than three quarters of the respondents have provided a positive response either in terms of expressing an agreement or a strong agreement). However, there is also **one negative response** that needs to be considered.

Search Question #8

The values per filter help to make a more specific selection and narrow down the number of search results presented.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **whether the filters make it easier to select and narrow down the search results**, there appears to be some kind of **diversity** in the responses provided.

We **need to dive deeper into our respondents' insights** and **seek some further and detailed feedback** in order to find out what the actual situation is here.

Search Question #9

I find the option to combine multiple values per filter or more than one filters helpful when it comes to narrowing down the number of search results.

6 responses

Rating scale used...

- 1: Completely disagree
- 2: Disagree
- 3: Neither agree nor disagree
- 4: Agree
- 5: Completely agree

Interpretation of the responses provided

From the responses provided with regard to **using multiple values per filter or multiple filter values to narrow down the number of search results**, it can be said that the **responses made available lean towards the positive direction**. However, there are also **two neutral responses** (one third of the responses provided in total) that need to be considered.

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